

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 08.10.2018 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Ravi Bhaskar	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Haritha Chandran	Member
7. Ms. Shristina Subba	Member
8. Dr. Sathyajith Karanth	Member
9. Dr. Sangeetha	Member
10. Ms. Laveena D'Souza	Member
11. Ms. Swathi D	External Member
12. Dr. Shwetha B	External Member

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 06.03.2018.
2. Revise Few Topics in the Course of 'Anaesthesia and Operation Theatre Technology'.
3. Discussion regarding M.Sc. Course in Allied Health Sciences.
4. Modification of End Semester Examination Scheme.
5. Any other Item with the Permission of the Chair.

The Chairman welcomed all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting there after deliberated on agenda as had been approved by the Chairperson.

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 06.03.2018. As per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Finalized Updated order of Credit Scheme as already approved in the Last BOS for Academic Session 2017-18 and Changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 3: Discussion regarding the Syllabi of the Courses of Allied Health Sciences was made and finalized. All the Course Titles in every proficiency field have been approved.

Agenda No. 4: As per the suggestion of Dr. Ravi Bhaskar, subsidiary subject Medical Ethics has been added to the Allied Health Department Renal Dialysis Technology. Changes were approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 5: To Revise the Topics of the course of 'Medical Laboratory Technology' was suggested by Dr. Ravi Bhaskar and Sr. Faculty Mr. Naveen Bappanadu.

The Suggestion was made as follows:

Sl. No.	Semester	Subject	Unit	Addition	Deletion	Remarks
1	I	Biochemistry	1	-	Deletion of Fundamental Chemistry	-
			2	Addition of Enzymes, Acid base balance	-	-
			3	Addition of Nutrition, Blood chemistry, Urine chemistry	-	-
			4	-	Deletion of Units of measurement	-
			5	Addition of Clinical Biochemistry	Deletion of Solutions	-

The Revised Topics were confirmed and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

Agenda No. 6: Discussion regarding the Course Outcomes (Cos) – Programs Outcomes (POs) – Program Specific Outcomes (PSOs), Attainments for 2018-19 (Odd Semester 2018 and Even Semester 2019). The same was approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 7: The MOOCs to be introduced during the Academic Session 2019-20 for all batches of ECE. Board has suggested giving only one MOOC of Computer Vision instead of two. So Introduction of Computer Vision has been deleted. Rest all courses were approved.

Agenda No. 8: Open Elective floated for 6th Semester of 3 credits (3-0-0) for 2017 batch will be considered as Professional elective. Few more suggestions regarding revising few topics of various Allied Health courses was discussed and decided to consider as soon as possible.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Dr. Vishrutha K V, Member, Board of Studies.

Dr. Ravi Bhaskar,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Members present:

Dr. Ravi Bhaskar

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Pavanchand Attavar

Dr. Vishrutha K V

Ms. Haritha Chandran

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